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HYPERTROPHIC PYLORIC STENOSIS IN THE STRUCTURE OF CAUSES OF GASTROINTESTINAL DISORDERS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

Abstract.

Hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is one of the most common causes of obstruction of the upper gastrointestinal tract in infants during the first months of life and remains a pressing issue in pediatric surgery and pediatrics. The disease is characterized by progressive hypertrophy of the circular muscle layer of the pyloric section of the stomach, leading to impaired evacuation of gastric contents, repeated vomiting, and the development of metabolic disorders. The aim of this study is to summarize current data on the epidemiology, pathogenetic mechanisms, clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and treatment of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis. A systematic review of the literature was conducted, including review articles, meta-analyses, and clinical studies. The role of genetic, neurohumoral, and other factors in the development of the disease, as well as the effectiveness of modern surgical and conservative treatment methods, were analyzed. The data obtained confirm that early diagnosis and timely surgical intervention ensure a favorable prognosis and minimal risk of complications.

Keywords: pyloric stenosis, gastrointestinal disorders, infants, vomiting, pylorotomy.

Hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is a classic pathology of early childhood, most often manifesting in the first 2–8 weeks of life. Despite many years of study, the etiology and pathogenesis of this disease remain the subject of active research. The clinical significance of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is due to the risk of rapid development of dehydration, electrolyte disturbances, and metabolic alkalosis, which, if left untreated, can be life-threatening to the child. The risk of developing this disease is significantly increased by maternal smoking during pregnancy. Infants who were exposed to certain macrolide antibiotics (e.g., erythromycin [2]), [3] during the first few weeks of life, especially during the first two weeks, have a significantly increased incidence of the disease. [5] Bottle-fed infants had a 4.6 times higher risk of developing hypertrophic pyloric stenosis than infants who were not bottle-fed. This result adds to the evidence in favor of exclusive breastfeeding in the first months after birth. [4] Pyloric stenosis occurs in 2-5 cases per 1,000 live births annually. It is more common in boys, with a male-to-female ratio of 4:1. Firstborns were observed in 43% of cases. [6]

Recent studies confirm the important role of neurohumoral mechanisms in the development of the disease. One of the key factors is considered to be a deficiency of neuronal NO synthase and, accordingly, a decrease in the production of NO, the main inhibitory neurotransmitter in the gastrointestinal tract. This leads to an increase in the tone of the smooth muscles of the pylorus and a loss of normal relaxation. Cajal's interstitial cells play a special role in coordinating gastric mo-

tility. A decrease in their number and functional activity in the pyloric section leads to peristaltic dyscoordination and maintains pyloric spasm. Hormonal factors also play a role in the pathogenesis of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis. Elevated gastrin levels stimulate muscle cell proliferation and contribute to the progression of pyloric sphincter hypertrophy. Genetic studies confirm the polygenic nature of the disease and its association with genes that regulate neuromuscular transmission and smooth muscle development.

The current level of development of ultrasound diagnostics and surgical treatment methods has significantly improved the outcomes of such patients. At the same time, the accumulation of new data on the molecular and neurophysiological mechanisms of pyloric stenosis formation requires systematization from the perspective of evidence-based medicine.

Analyzing the clinical picture, it should be noted that the classic symptom of pyloric stenosis is progressive vomiting without bile, which occurs after feeding. Children often remain hungry after episodes of vomiting. With a prolonged course of the disease, signs of dehydration, weight loss, and delayed physical development are observed. Repeated loss of gastric juice leads to the development of hypochloremic, hypokalemic metabolic alkalosis, which is a characteristic laboratory sign of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis [6] and is important for preoperative preparation.

The diagnosis of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is based on a combination of instrumental and clinical examination methods. Physical examination findings such as palpation of a tumor described as olive-like are

important, but ultrasound diagnostics is much more informative. [6], [7] Ultrasound examination is the method of choice for diagnosing hypertrophic pyloric stenosis due to its high sensitivity and specificity. The main ultrasound criteria are a thickening of the pyloric muscle layer of more than 3 mm and an elongation of the pyloric canal of more than 15–18 mm. The method allows not only to confirm the diagnosis, but also to assess the functional state of the pylorus, in particular the absence or significant slowing of gastric emptying. In doubtful cases, it is possible to use X-ray contrast examination of the upper gastrointestinal tract using barium, which shows characteristic signs of contrast delay and a “thread-like” lumen of the pyloric canal. Laboratory diagnostics are of auxiliary importance and are aimed at detecting electrolyte and acid-base disturbances, primarily hypochloremic metabolic alkalosis. Hypochloremia was observed in approximately one-third of cases. [6] Repeated loss of gastric juice leads to the development of hypochloremic, hypokalemic metabolic alkalosis, which is a characteristic laboratory sign of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis and is important for preoperative preparation.

Treatment of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis is mainly surgical. After correcting the water-salt balance, pylorotomy is performed to restore patency. Ramsted pylorotomy is most often used, which is currently the gold standard. [8] This operation ensures the elimination of functional obstruction without damaging the integrity of the mucous membrane; recovery after surgery is fairly quick, and analysis of studies on surgical interventions performed in regional hospitals shows that the method is safe and affordable, with oral feeding restored in 76% of infants within 24 hours. However, surgery is not always necessary. For medical treatment, atropine is used, administered intravenously at 0.01 mg/kg 6 times a day before feeding, [9] which reduces pyloric spasm and achieves effective feeding. Children who were successfully treated with atropine had the same weight within a year as those who underwent surgery. Drug treatment takes much longer but has its advantages in cases where there are contraindications to surgery and does not have complications such as surgical intervention.

Conclusion.

Hypertrophic pyloric stenosis remains an important problem in pediatrics and pediatric surgery. Current data confirm the multifactorial nature of the disease with a leading role played by neuromuscular and hormonal mechanisms. Ultrasound diagnostics has high specificity and accuracy, ensuring early detection of pathology, and pyloromyotomy is an effective and safe treatment method with an excellent prognosis, provided that intervention is timely.

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